

Stability Constants of Humic Acids and their Phosphorylated Derivatives with Cu^{2+} and Al^{3+}

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Measurements of stability constant of the complexes of natural and synthetic Humic Acids and their phosphorylated derivatives with Cu^{2+} and Al^{3+} ions indicate that at a particular pH, Al^{3+} -complexes are more stable than their Cu^{2+} complexes and the complexes are more stable at higher pH.

THE fate of a particular metal ion, that whether it will be precipitated, translocated or taken up by plant roots for their biological processes often depends upon the stability of soil organic matter-metal complexes. An idea of the stability constants of different soil organic matter metal complexes will, therefore, help the soil scientists to understand better the role of these compounds in such systems.

Himes and Barber¹ in their study of soil organic matter-metal combinations assumed that the organic matter (o.m.) contains only one type of adsorption centre and the chelation follows a Langmuir type of isotherm, which could be extrapolated to give the concentration of complexing sites. By this method they obtained log K values 3.4 to 5.6 for organic matter-zinc complexes. Broadbent and Otto² compared the relative stabilities of different metal organic matter combinations and found the order Cu-complex > Ba-complex = Ca-complex $\geq$ Mg-complex.

The exchange method as developed by Schubert³⁻⁵ was applied to soil organic matter-metal complexes by Miller and Ohlrogge⁶, Randhawa and Broadbent⁷, Schnitzer and Skinner^{8,9} and recently by Ardakni and Stevenson¹⁰ and Adhikari and Hazra¹¹.

The object of the present study is to determine the log K values of o.m. [o.m. = natural and synthetic H.A., phosphorylate derivatives of synthetic and natural products]—metal complexes at two different pH by improved ion-exchange method as developed by Ardakni and Stevenson¹⁰.

Theory

When a particular amount of cation exchanger is equilibrated with metal ions in solution the quantity of cation bound to the cation exchanger (M_R) is proportional to the concentration of free metal ions (M_f) in solution over a wide range of concentration.

$$\frac{M_R}{M_f} = \lambda_0 = \frac{\alpha_0 v}{(100 - \alpha_0)g}$$

where

λ_0 = distribution coefficient in the absence of chelating agent,

α_0 = % of total metal used which is bound to exchanger,

$(100 - \alpha_0)$ = % of total metal used which remained in solution,

v = volume of solution,

and g = weight of cation exchanger.

From measurement of relative effects under these conditions in the absence of complexing agents and in the presence of different concentrations of complexing materials it is possible to determine the formation constant without any knowledge of the specific reaction between metals and exchange resins. To accomplish this it is necessary to keep the solution at constant temperature, ionic strength, and pH, volume and weight of adsorbent. The exchanger must be previously saturated with the electrolyte to maintain constant ionic strength.

For the general case where metal ions M react with an organic ligand A , to form a metal-organic matter complex $MjAi$, the usual law of equilibrium apply.

Stability constant,

$$k = \frac{[MjAi]}{(M)^j(A)^i} \quad \dots (1)$$

Actually pH factor should be a part of stability constant, since the reaction is metal ion + chelating agent $\rightleftharpoons$ metal chelate + H^+ . As the reaction is reversible, the stability const. k should be expressed as

$$k = \frac{[\text{Metal chelate}] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Metal ion}] \times [\text{chelating agent}]}$$

The lower the pH , therefore, the less tendency there should be for metal chelate to form¹².

The effect of pH on the stability constant of metal chelates has, therefore, been studied.

To determine the stability constant of the metal chelates by the equation (1) several unknown must be determined and can be solved by a graphical approach. From equation (1)

$$[M_j A_i] = k[M]^j[A]^i \quad \dots (2)$$

Since there are ' j ' metal ions per mole of the complex $M_j A_i$, the concentration of the combined metal ion (M_c) will be $[M_c] = j[M_j A_i]$; So from equation (2)

$$[M_c] = jk[M_f]^j[A]^i$$

or,

$$\text{Log } [M_c] = \text{log } j + \text{log } k + j \text{ log } [M_f] + i \text{ log } [A].$$

' j ' and ' k ' are constants for a small range of $[M_f]$ concentration, we have, therefore,

$$\text{Log } [M_c] = C + j \text{ log } [M_f] + i \text{ log } [A]$$

or,

$$\frac{\partial[\text{log } (M_c)]}{\partial[\text{log } (M_f)]A} = j \quad \dots (3)$$

and,

$$\frac{\partial[\text{log } (M_c)]}{\partial[\text{log } (A)]M_f} = i \quad \dots (4)$$

Equation (3) indicates that if A is kept constant, a plot of $\text{log } [M_c]$ vs $\text{log } [M_f]$ will be a straight line with a slope ' j ' and an intercept, $1a$,

So,

$$1a = \text{log } k + \text{log } j + i \text{ log } [A].$$

Similarly from equation (4) a value of ' i ' and $1b$ can be obtained,

where, $1b = \text{log } k + \text{log } j + j \text{ log } [M_f]$.

Hence the value of k is calculated.

Experimental

The chemical analyses of Humic Acids (synthetic and natural) and their phosphorylate derivatives are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF ORGANIC MATTER
(NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC H.A.)

Elements %	Analysate, %			
	Kalimpong H.A.	Kalimp. Phospho. H.A.	Synthetic H.A.	Synth. phospho. H.A.
O	48.2	44.45	52.31	48.31
H	5.18	3.20	7.02	5.95
N	1.95	2.02	5.05	3.52
P	—	0.96	—	1.20

0.5 ml to 2.5 ml solution of CuSO_4 of known strengths were taken in 25 ml volumetric flasks, and 1 ml of organic matter colloid was added to each of the volumetric flasks followed by the addition of 2 ml N NaCl solution in each. pH of different solutions were kept at 4.00 by adding required amount of dil. HCl . A separate set of experiments were adjusted at pH 6.00 by adding NaOH solution. Known weights of Na -saturated Amberlite I.R.-120 resin were taken in 100 ml ground glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks. Solutions from volumetric flasks were transferred to these flasks and the contents were shaken for 20 hr adjusting the pH from time to time. It was then allowed to equilibrate for a further period of 24 hr. Solutions from these flasks were then transferred to 25 ml volumetric flasks quantitatively and volumes made upto the mark. 5 ml of these solutions were taken out, organic matter decomposed by alkaline H_2O_2 and the metal ions were estimated by EDTA at required pH . The experiments were repeated for Al -complex. Identical experiments were conducted at pH 4.0 and 6.0 without using the organic matter to evaluate the resin adsorption curves.

Results are shown in Table 2 and ' i ' and ' f ' were calculated from Figures (All are not shown here except for Kalimpong in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Kalimpong H.A.— Cu^{2+} at pH 4.00.

Results and Discussion

From the Table shown, it is evident that the value of ' i ' is nearly equal to unity but the value of ' j ' appreciably differs from unity. This indicates that the complex is mononuclear with respect to the organic ligand but metal ion is not the core of the complex. It is the organic ligand around which the metal ions cluster¹⁰. This is possible in such combinations because humic acid and its phosphorylated derivatives are heterogeneous in structure possessing a larger number of complexing sites. These sites

TABLE 2

$\mu = 0.2$, Total volume = 10.0 ml, Temp. = 28°, Wt. of resin = 0.01 g. Concentration of humic acids— A_1, A_2, A_3 , pH = 4.0.
 $A_1 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles); $A_2 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles);
 $A_3 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles)

(1) *Kalimpong H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
5.0	6.03	6.7	7.35			
6.0	7.25	8.0	8.82	1.0	1.2	3.95
6.5	8.04	8.9	9.8			
7.0	8.73	9.7	10.6			

(2) *Phosphorylated Kalimpong H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
5.0	6.73	7.4	8.24			
6.0	8.8	9.7	10.5	1.0	1.49	4.90
6.5	9.95	10.94	11.9			
7.0	11.1	12.2	13.3			

(3) *Synthetic H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 4.9 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
4.70			11.76			
4.99	5.01					
5.01		9.77				
5.75			15.74			
5.89		12.02		0.93	1.24	4.87
5.93	6.30					
8.13			24.00			
8.32	9.77					
9.10		19.95				

(4) *Phosphorylated Synthetic H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 4.9 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
5.0	5.2	6.4	8.4			
6.5	7.5	9.5	12.5	0.8	1.42	4.68
7.0	8.3	10.6	14.0			
7.8	9.6	12.45	16.4			

(5) *Synthetic H.A.—Al³⁺*

$A_1 = 4.9 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
5.0	12.8	15.8	26.2			
6.0	16.0	19.6	32.6	0.90	1.19	5.30
6.5	17.6	21.6	35.9			
7.0	19.2	23.6	39.2			

(6) *Kalimpong H.A.—Al³⁺*

$A_1 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_2 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_3 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
5.0	2.08	2.28	2.49			
6.0	2.58	2.84	3.10	1.0	1.20	4.50
6.5	2.84	3.13	3.41			
7.0	3.11	3.41	3.72			

pH = 6.0

(7) *Kalimpong H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_2 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_3 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
0.8	2.94	3.24	3.52			
1.4	8.9	9.8	10.7	1.0	1.40	5.49
2.0	14.9	16.1	17.5			
2.4	18.9	20.8	22.65			

(8) *Phosphorylated Kalimpong H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_2 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_3 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
0.8	0.55	0.62	0.69			
1.4	1.50	1.70	1.88	1.1	1.8	6.60
2.0	2.85	3.23	3.6			
2.4	3.97	4.50	4.96			

(9) *Synthetic H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 4.9 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
0.8	1.09	1.22	2.37			
1.4	2.51	2.81	5.48	1.9	1.46	6.65
2.0	4.35	4.81	9.38			
2.4	5.7	6.31	12.30			

(10) *Phosphorylated synthetic H.A.—Cu²⁺*

$A_1 = 5.3 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}$ (M); $A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
0.8	0.58	0.63	1.17			
1.4	1.75	1.87	3.57	1.09	1.95	7.9
2.0	3.57	3.80	7.30			
2.4	5.14	5.38	10.5			

(11) *Kalimpong H.A.—Al³⁺*

$A_1 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_2 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (M); $A_3 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (M)

$M_f \times 10^{-4}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}$ (M) for			<i>i</i> (Average)	<i>j</i> (Average)	log <i>k</i> (Average)
	A_1	A_2	A_3			
0.8	4.7	5.2	5.7			
1.4	9.5	10.4	11.4	1.1	1.26	5.98
2.0	14.86	16.3	17.8			
2.4	18.7	20.8	22.4			

(12) Synthetic H.A.—Al³⁺

$$A_1 = 4.9 \times 10^{-5}(M); A_2 = 6.03 \times 10^{-5}(M); A_3 = 10.0 \times 10^{-5}(M)$$

$\frac{Mf}{\times 10^{-4}}$ (M)	$M_C \times 10^{-4}(M)$ for			i (Average)	j (Average)	log k (Average)
	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃			
0.8	5.24	6.44	10.7			
1.4	12.1	14.9	24.7	1.11	1.50	7.00
2.0	20.7	25.5	42.3			
2.4	27.1	33.4	55.5			

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fix a number of metal ions by various types of bonds. Some of these may be co-ordinated bonds, others may be either ionic, covalent or of Vanderwaals' type.

Log *k* values indicate that the phosphorylated humic acid—metal complexes are more stable than humic acid—metal complexes and the value of log *k* increases as the pH is raised from 4.0 to 6.0. This shows that the stability is pH-dependent. The stability of these complexes at a particular pH follows the order Al-complex > Cu-complex which is in accordance with those of other workers¹⁶.

Phosphorylation of humic acids aids to introduce phosphorous in H.A. as evidenced by the increase of molecular weight of the phosphoryl derivative [molecular weight increases from 1020 to 1860 for Kalimpong HA and its phospho-derivative. B.E.C. of phosphorylated humic acid also shows some increase in value]. Thus phosphorylated humic acids can bind more metal ions and the strength of the bond will be high because both phosphate ion and the bonding sites of humic acid will be linked to metal ion¹³.

The higher stability of the complexes at higher pH may be due one or both of the causes as explained below :

(1) Formation of hydroxylated type of bonds as evidenced in potentiometric study¹⁶, and

(2) At low pH, H⁺ competes with the metal ion for donor groups and at high pH, H⁺ are removed from the reaction sites and OH⁻ competes with the donor groups for metal ions¹². The relative solubilities of metal hydroxides is a determinant factor in

chelate stability and those metals which form insoluble hydroxides may not be easily chelated¹². Al³⁺ and Cu²⁺ both undergo solution at higher pH and form more stable complexes. Moreover higher pH has got some influence on the basicity of nitrogen group in chelating agents¹⁴. Humic acid contains some nitrogen groups¹⁵ whose basicity increases with increase in pH and this enhances the chance for further co-ordination.

Log *k* values obtained in the present study are higher than reported by other workers^{6,7,15}. This is most probably due to the fact that simplified assumptions in calculating log *k* values were made in their earlier publications. In the present study the method as used assumes only a single reaction between organic ligand and metal ion. This may not be probably true and so has allowances for criticism till a better technique is available.

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